

DENSIFYING EFFECT ON THE PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBE FILM

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ABSTRACT

As a kind of two-dimensional carbon nanotube (CNT) macroscopic material, CNT film fabricated from the chemical vapor deposition (CVD)-grown spinnable CNT array generally has better orientation and less impurities, could transfer the properties of CNT efficiently, possessing great potential in mechanical, electrical, thermal and optical application. In this paper, continuous single layer CNT sheet was drawn from super-aligned spinnable CNT array and wound by a rotating mandrel to fabricate pure CNT film. By controlling the main fabricating process parameters, the densifying degree and tensile properties of pure CNT film were adjusted, meanwhile the effects of densifying process parameters on the mechanical properties of CNT film were also studied. Based on these, optimized densifying assembling process conditions which would be beneficial to aligning and dense packing of CNTs with less-porosity were presented. Besides, the influences of different solvent densifying approaches on CNT film's structure and tensile properties were also discussed. It is found that comparing with the previous reported spray-winding densifying method, an innovative solvent evaporation-induced densifying method could efficiently avoid the air-disturbance during the fabrication, assemble CNTs into much denser structure with good flexibility, better alignment, and increase the tensile properties and electrical conductivity significantly. As a convenient approach, it is considered to provide a reasonable optimized fabrication route for high performance CNT films.

1 INTRODUCTION

The unique mechanical and multi-functional properties of carbon nanotube (CNT) have motivated considerable interests in assembling CNTs based macroscopic materials in order to take advantage of the properties of CNTs in the greatest extent. CNT film is a kind of two-dimensional plane macroscopic CNTs structure which has been a research focus for many years. At the early stage, vacuum filtration from CNTs solution^[1] and pushing the aligned chemical vapor deposition (CVD)-grown CNT arrays down^[2] are the two main approaches to fabricate the CNT films. Recently, the super-aligned spinnable CNT array makes it possible to drawing continuous CNT sheet directly^[3], thus it opened a new door for more controllable film's fabrication. In the separately drawing process, the catalysts and impurities are mostly left on the substrate, resulting in a better oriented and more pure CNT film which shows great potential as a high performance CNT material. For example, materials containing array-based CNT film have shown their promising performance and application in the areas of battery^[4,5], photoelectric device^[6,7], electrode^[8,9] and so on.

As improved structures always bring significant advances in both mechanical and functional performances, many researches have also been carried out on the structural adjustment and properties enhancement. For example, by spray-winding resin solutions, a CNT/poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) composite film with strength and modulus up to 1.8 GPa and 45 GPa was prepared^[10]. Combined with hot-pressing treatment, a CNT/epoxy composite film with strength of 1.5 GPa and modulus of 59 GPa was obtained^[11]. Apart from these work, it should be noticed that the densification of as-spun CNT film is always a necessary and important procedure for producing CNT film, in which the assembling status of nanotubes could be greatly adjusted. However, the related reports are quite few and more efforts should be devoted to study the densifying process and its effects on the CNT film's properties.

In this paper, the densifying effects were studied in two aspects: densifying winding process and solvent densifying method. Firstly, CNT films were fabricated at different winding line speed to study the effect of fabricating parameter and obtain optimized fabricating condition. Then a new evaporation-induced densifying method was presented to find the effect of solvent densifying approach on the packing structure and film properties. The results show that the film structure and properties could be effectively improved by appropriate process optimization and the modified solvent densifying method.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Fabrication of CNT films

Spinnable CVD-grown CNT arrays were used to draw the CNT films, and the CNT arrays were grown by the same method as our group reported before^[12]. The CNT in array has 2 ~4 walls, with diameter of 3 ~5 nm, and length of ~200 μm . Due to the Van der Waals forces, continuous CNT sheet could be horizontally drawn from the vertically aligned CNT array and directly wound onto a rotating polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) mandrel to obtain the as-spun CNT film.

Then the as-spun films were densified with ethanol by two approaches: spray-winding and stretch-dip-drying. For the spray-winding CNT film, as shown in Figure 1a, during the winding process, ethanol was simultaneously sprayed to densify the winding sheets at the opposite side of the rotating mandrel using an air brush (Badge NH200). For the stretch-dip-drying CNT film, after winding process, the film was dipped in solvents and quickly-dried under tension for several cycles (Figure 1b). For convenient, the CNT film densified by spray-winding ethanol was denoted as SW-film, the CNT film densified by stretch-dip-drying ethanol was denoted as SDD-film. After finishing the densifying process, the CNT films were dried and pressed to remove the solvents completely.

Figure 1: The schematic illustration of the densification procedure for (a) spray-winding method and (b) stretch-dip-drying method.

2.2 Mechanical Testing

For the tensile test of the CNT films, the as-prepared films were cut into small rectangular pieces with 2.6 cm in length and 0.5 mm in width, which were glued onto a window-frame with a rectangular opening in the center. The gage length was 6 mm for all samples. The thickness of the CNT films was tested by a micrometer caliper. Mechanical testing was performed on a mechanical testing machine (Instron 3365) with a load cell of 100 N at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min. Each type of CNT film was tested at least 10 times.

2.3 Characterization

The alignment degree of the CNT films was characterized by the decrease of normalized G' band intensity from polarized Raman spectroscopy (HORIBA LabRAM-HR) when the polarization axis of the incident laser beam was change from parallel to perpendicular with the film^[11, 13]. XRD (PANalytical X'Pert PRO MRD) was also used to evaluate the CNT alignment degree^[14, 15].

The electrical conductivity of the CNT films was tested with a multifunction digital four-probe tester (Jingge ST-2258A).

FIB/SEM (FEI Helios NanoLab 600i) was used to get the thin cross sectional film sample for TEM (JEOL 2100F) observation. The films surface morphology was observed by SEM (Hitachi S-4800 and FEI QuanTa 400 FEG).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 THE EFFECTS OF WINDING PROCESS

In the winding process of CNT film, the rotating mandrel provides the drawing force on the CNT sheet, which will further influences the waviness and stacking status of CNTs in the film. The line speed of CNT sheet can reflect the drawing force and could be tuned by mandrel and rotating speed. To investigate the drawing force's effect on the film's tensile properties, CNT films were wound at the line speed of 16π cm/min, 32π cm/min, 48π cm/min and 64π cm/min, respectively. Then the tensile properties of films were tested and shown in Figure 2. It is obviously that whthin a certain range, the tensile strength and modulus of CNT films will increase with the growing line speed. To be more detailed, the CNT film wound at the speed of 16π cm/min only has strength of 1.0 GPa and modulus of 25.2 GPa. While the line speed rises to 32π cm/min, the strength and modulus increase to 1.1 GPa and 38.8 GPa. At the line speed of 48π cm/min, the average strength and modulus of CNT film reach the highest value of 1.2 GPa and 44.8 GPa. However, when the line speed continued goes to 64π cm/min, the tensile properties drop sharply, with strength and modulus only to be 0.7 GPa and 20.8 GPa, which are even worsor than the properties of films wound at the speed of 16π cm/min. This is a little different from the previous reports of Liu^[16], in which the properties of film are believed increase firstly and then stay stable as the winding speed goes up.

Figure 2: (a) The tensile strength and (b) modulus of CNT films wound at different line speed.

It is suggested that when the speed is low, the increasing line speed generates larger drawing force on the CNT sheet, which can improve the CNTs alignment in film, reduce tube waviness and bridges, stimulate denser packing of CNTs and provide more efficient load transmitting, so the tensile properties will be enhanced significantly. However, after the line speed increasing over a certain degree, the drawing force becomes so large and exceeds the inter-tube interactions, which causes easily sheet splitting and is adverse for keep the stable uniform distribution of CNTs. Moreover, solution amount sprayed on film per unit will decrease under too fast winding speed, weakening the solvent's infiltration and clustering effect on CNTs. These drawbacks are detrimental to the dense packing of CNTs and the tensile properties of films. It can be observed that under extremely fast line speed, CNT sheet splits soon and rapidly fracture due to the split spreading. These results revealed that appropriate winding speed should be chosen to obtain uniform and oriented CNT film, which has higher tensile strength and modulus. Also, appropriate stretching and modified densification method

could be considered to apply on the film, in order to further improve the ordered structure and enhance the properties.

3.2 THE EFFECTS OF DENSIFYING METHOD

With above inspiration in mind, a new stretch-dip-drying method is presented to densify the as-spun film. After densification, the surface morphology of SDD-film was studied with the aid of SEM, and the SEM image of SW-film was also given for comparison. As shown in Figure 3a, small and loose bundles among with lots of voids appear on the surface of SW-film, while for SDD-film in Figure 3b, the bundles sizes are much larger and neat.

Figure 3: The SEM images of (a) SW-film and (b) SDD-film.

With the aid of FIB, ultrathin cross-sections samples were prepared and observed under TEM. As shown in Figure 4, many voids can be seen in the cross-section of SW-film (pointed by the arrows), and CNTs tend to be loose stacked. While CNTs in SDD-film closely packed into elliptical bundles, and the image shows only few voids and un-oriented tiny bundles (pointed by the arrows) distribution. Moreover, tube walls deform slightly in the films, which is beneficial to more efficient tube-contact and load transmitting.

Figure 4: TEM images of the cross-sectional morphology for (a) SW-film and (b) SDD-film.

To evaluate the film alignment more accurate, polarized Raman spectroscopy and XRD were used to characterize the film. As previous reported, G' peak intensity is strongly dependent on the CNT orientation, so the G' peak intensities at different polarized angles were tested and fitted to evaluate the alignment degree (Figure 5a). The SW-film's alignment degree is calculated to be 0.46, while this value of SDD-film is 0.62. This indicates that SDD-film has better alignment than SW-film. What's more, an azimuth-scan at $2\theta \approx 22^\circ$ was performed on the film as in Figure 5b and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) is calculated. The FWHM for SW-film and SDD-film are 33° and 27° , respectively. As narrow FWHM always means better alignment, the results also indicate that SDD-film is more orientated, which is same with the conclusion drawn from the polarized Raman experiments.

Figure 5: (a) Polarized Raman spectra of SW-film and SDD-film at 0°, 20°, 40°, 60° and 90°. (b) X-ray intensity of SW-film and SDD-film vs the azimuth.

According to the above results, we use 3D models in Figure 6 to describe the different CNT packing features in the films densified by different methods. For SW-film, the curly CNTs loosely packed into small bundles which have much voids entrapped and worse alignment. But in the SDD-film model, nanotubes are mostly straightened and assembled into large, dense and more oriented bundles. The differences in packing status are related with the various processing conditions. For the spray-winding process, the spraying tiny drops limit the infiltrating effect and the shrink of film in width is also confined. Besides, the airflow generated by spray is quite strong, always interfering the CNTs arrangement in film. In contrast, for the stretch-dip-drying approach, completely infiltration under stretching promotes the aligned gathering of CNTs. Then the quenching-like drying treatment stimulates closely packing of CNTs and shrinks the film as a whole due to the evaporation and the strong capillary effect.

Figure 6: The 3D models of (a) SW-film and (b) SDD-film.

The tensile properties were also tested to study the effect of densifying method. The SDD-film shows tensile strength of 2.58 GPa and tensile modulus of 124 GPa, much higher than the SW-film's tensile properties mentioned in the 3.1 section (i.e. strength of 1.2 GPa and modulus of 44.8 GPa). The enhancements are ascribed to the improved structure and modified densification, because the stretch-dip-drying treatment could considerably improve the mechanical-favorable structure features: tube straightness, superior orientation and dense packing. To be detailed, tube-sliding is considered to be the main reason for film tensile failure^[17], and the frictional resistance greatly depends on the inter-tube contact degree^[18]. In this case, large aligned bundle and dense packing can enlarge the inter-tube contact area, and make the inter-tube load transmitting more efficiently, which further improves the mechanical properties of CNT films. Furthermore, the improved packing structure also increases the film's electrical conductivity effectively, as the SDD-film shows an electrical conductivity of 318S/cm along the film alignment direction, while the SW-film only has an electrical conductivity of 116S/cm in the same direction. The ameliorating in both mechanical and electrical properties exhibits the potentials of the new evaporation-induced densifying approach in fabricating high performance CNT films.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Summarily, the effects of densifying winding process and solvent densifying method were studied in this paper. By comparing CNT films wound at different line speed, it is revealed that appropriate faster line speed would provide larger drawing force, which is good for straightening nanotubes and tightening the CNT packing assembly, thus enhancing the tensile properties. Then by densifying the as-spun films with a new stretch-dip-drying method, CNT film with improved tensile properties (i.e. strength of 2.58 GPa and modulus of 124 GPa) and electrical conductivity (i.e. 318 S/cm) was obtained. The SEM, TEM, Polarized Raman and XRD analysis attributed the main mechanism of the densifying modification on the film's structure and performance to some aspects, i.e. fewer voids, better alignment and denser packing structure, which together improved the load transmitting among tubes effectively.

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